

Supplementary Information

Global pathways to sustainable development to 2030 and beyond

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Supplementary Methods

Supplementary Methods 1: The FeliX model

FeliX¹ is a system dynamics model² that simulates complex interactions in the nexus of ten sectors: population, education, economy, energy, water, land, food and diet change, carbon cycle, climate, and biodiversity (Extended Data Figure 1). The model captures underpinning feedback mechanisms of physical and anthropogenic change between these sectors based on integral differential equations. FeliX has been used previously for exploring global energy and land-use emissions pathways³, the diet shift in food systems⁴, and for evaluating socio-environmental impacts in Earth observation systems⁵. FeliX was calibrated with global historical data¹ from 1900 to 2015 with results reported at the global average. The full description of FeliX modules and their equations are available online in FeliX original documentation¹.

Population and education. The population module computes the male and female population size of 5-year age cohorts between the ages 0 and 100+ by capturing the dynamics of population growth and population ageing. The population module also computes change in life expectancy with impacts for health services, food, and climate risk. Population is the core module in FeliX impacting, directly or indirectly, all other sectors such as energy demand, water use, effects on fertilizer use, and food consumption. The population size at different age cohorts feeds into the education module to compute the population of primary, secondary, and tertiary education graduates through the feedback loops among the enrolment rate, graduation rate, and persistency to eventually reach the last grade of each education level. The accumulation of the educated population in all age cohorts between 15 and 64, multiplied by a labour force participation fraction computes the labour force input for the economy module. Population and education are calibrated with the historical demographic data from the UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs⁶.

Economy. The economy module is modelled as a Cobb-Douglas production function where total Gross World Product (GWP) is computed from labour input, total capital input from energy and non-energy sector, and total factor of productivity from energy and non-energy technologies. FeliX further develops the Cobb-Douglas function to incorporate the impacts of changes in ecosystems and climate change on the economic outputs. Given that human development should include measures beyond economic advances. FeliX also computes an alternative measure called Human Development Index which is an indicator of health (life expectancy), educational attainment, and income. The economy module is calibrated with historical statistics of world economy⁷ and UNDP⁸.

Energy. The energy module models energy demand as a function of GDP per capita and population. The energy consumption is modelled through the energy market share of different sources by capturing the price competitive mechanisms between three fossil (i.e., coal, oil, gas) and three renewable (i.e., solar, wind, biomass) sources of energy. Energy production from each fossil source is modelled as a function of energy demand, the market share of energy source, the effect of investment on energy production, and the identified fossil energy resource. FeliX models the technological advancement in discovery of fossil resources and investment in exploration to account for undiscovered resources that can be identified in the future. FeliX also models the technological improvement for the recovery of fossil resources. The basic model structure for renewable energy sources is similar to fossil fuels, determined by five key submodules of available renewable resources (e.g., average sun radiation, wind available

area), the supply chain of installed capacity and their ageing process, the unit cost of production (e.g., the impact of wind and solar learning curve), available investment, and the technological efficiency and productivity (e.g., solar conversion efficiency, wind capacity factor). The energy module is calibrated with data from IEA⁹ and BP¹⁰.

Water. FeliX models the water sector through water scarcity, that is the balance between the supply of reliable water and water withdrawal. Water supply is a function of available water resources, a drought out rate, the impact of climate change, water withdrawal, and the recovery of water used in other sectors. Water withdrawal is for agriculture, industrial, and domestic sectors. Agricultural water withdrawal depends on irrigated and rainfed agricultural lands, industrial water withdrawal depends on the GDP (economic activities), and domestic water withdrawal depends on both population and the GDP (wealth). The water module is calibrated with historical data from UNESCO¹¹.

Land. The land sector in FeliX is distributed among four categories of land-use: agricultural, forest, urban/industrial and 'other'. Different land-uses can be repurposed and converted to one another driven by demand for more agricultural lands (i.e., deforestation). The demand for agricultural land is balanced by increasing crop yields with fertilization. The agricultural land is divided into arable land, permanent crops, and permanent meadows and pastures. Arable land and permanent crops can be harvested to produce both food and feed as well as energy crops for biomass. Permanent meadows and pastures can only be used for feed production. The area of arable lands harvested is driven directly by food, feed and energy crops production and indirectly through food demand and biomass energy demand. The crops and livestock yields are modelled in FeliX as a function of input-neutral technological advancement, land management practices (impact of economy), water availability (impact of drought), nitrogen and prosperous fertilizer use, and climate change (impact of carbon concentration). The nitrogen and prosperous fertilizer use in agriculture, from commercial sources or produced with manure by pasture- and crop-based animals, is explicitly modelled in FeliX. Change in forest land cover is modelled through conversion with other land-uses as well as harvested forest areas needed for biomass energy production. The forest land fertility is modelled endogenously as a function of the effect of biodiversity, land management practices, climate change, and CO₂ concentration. The land module in FeliX is calibrated with global scale historical data from FAOSTAT¹².

Food and diet change. The food module in FeliX includes food demand (including waste fraction) and supply as well as diet shift in food consumption in population. Food demand is a function of food and feed fraction in demand, each of which is determined based on the size of population with animal-based and vegetable-based diets. Food supply is the sum of the supply of animal products including crop-based meat (poultry and pork), pasture-based meat (beef, sheep and goat), dairy and eggs and the supply of plant-based products including grains, pulses, oil crops, vegetable, roots, and fruits. Food production (related to food supply) depends on the area of harvested lands (from agricultural lands) and the crop and livestock yields (already discussed in the land module). The food consumption (related to food demand) is determined through linking to a model that relates human behaviour and dietary choices to different population segments (e.g., male and female, level of education). The diet change model⁴ explains various environmental actions to move towards more sustainable (less meat) diets based on two feedback mechanisms from psychological theories: diet change due to social norms and diet change due to a threat and coping appraisal. The latter is link to threats from climate events as an important feedback structure between physical and human systems.

The food and diet change module is calibrated with historical data from FAOSTAT¹² and Global Burden of Disease datasets¹³.

Carbon cycle. FeliX models CO₂ emissions endogenously based on the accumulation of carbon emissions from the energy and land sectors in the atmosphere. CO₂ emissions from land include emissions from agricultural activities (i.e., food production and land-use change to agricultural lands) as well as deforestation and forest conversion to managed forests and plantations. CO₂ emissions from the energy sector is computed explicitly based on the carbon intensity of energy production from fossil and renewable sources. Emissions from the energy sector also captures endogenously the effect improvement in carbon capture and storage technology and a desired emissions level from fossil fuels. Carbon is cycled through terrestrial reservoirs gradually absorbing into biosphere, pedosphere or oceans based on C-ROADS¹⁴, which is a climate model also used for climate impact analysis by UNFCCC. Carbon dissolution into ocean is through the mixed ocean layer (depth 0–100 m) and subsequently through four modelled deeper layers (100–400, 400–700, 700–2,000, and 2,000–2,800 m). See Walsh et al.³ for the modelled equations of carbon flux among different reservoirs. The carbon cycle module is calibrated with historical emissions data from the Carbon Dioxide Information Analysis Center¹⁵.

Climate. The climate module models CO₂ radiative forcing endogenously based on accumulated carbon (from land and energy) in atmosphere compared to the preindustrial level. The module models the radiative forcing of other gases (CH₄, N₂O, HFC) by linking FeliX to RCP scenarios¹⁶ and reading data from the projected forcing levels with the marker models of the shared socioeconomic pathways (i.e., IMAGE, GCAM, AIM, MESSAGE). The effect of total radiative forcing is associated with temperature anomalies as in the C-ROADS model. The surface temperature change is also affected by negative (cooling) feedback due to outbound longwave radiation as well as heat transfer from the atmosphere and mixed ocean layer to the four deep ocean layers.

Biodiversity. FeliX captures the effect of changes in land cover, land-use, and climate impact on the species carrying capacity (global average). The biodiversity module uses this carrying capacity to compute the mean species abundance from the species regeneration and extinction rates. The biodiversity module was calibrated with historical data from Secretariat of the Convention for Biological Diversity¹⁷.

Supplementary Methods 2: Pathway construction

We used the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs)^{18,19} as a basis to construct the modelled pathways. The SSPs^{18,19} are part of the next generation of climate scenarios²⁰, which represent the underlying socio-economic narratives of the futures, complementing the greenhouse gas concentration trajectories of the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs)¹⁶. The SSPs include a set of five consistent qualitative descriptions¹⁸ for plausible changes in the key drivers of the future such as human development, economy and lifestyle, policies and institutions, technology, and environment and natural resources, in 21st century.

We used the original SSPs as a basis to develop a set of (qualitative and quantitative) input assumptions for the Felix model. To integrate the SSPs into the Felix model, we began by elaborating a set of internally consistent and coherent ‘*pathway narratives*’ about five scenarios aligned with the assumptions under five SSP-RCP combinations from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Projects (CMIP6)²¹. Then we performed global sensitivity analysis to identify the

important socioeconomic and environmental drivers of future pathways (namely ‘*pathway drivers*’) in the model that were qualitatively described in our narratives. We calibrated the identified pathway drivers under the assumptions of pathway narratives and elaborated the future development quantitatively. Each of these steps are explained in detailed in Methods (main text) and as follows.

Describe pathway narratives. These storylines describe how the future could unfold driven by various uncertain (e.g., socioeconomic, demographic, technological, lifestyle) drivers. The combinations of these drivers create a wide range of plausible future developments of socio-economic and enviro-ecological systems, resulting in five storylines with different degrees of challenge for mitigation and adaption to climate change. We described these narratives in terms of 10 main pathway drivers adopted from the shared socioeconomic pathways (Supplementary Table 1). The description of future pathways in narratives informed the quantification of model input (qualitative and quantitative) assumptions in the next steps. The description of future pathways was aligned with the original SSP storylines¹⁸ (which provided a general scenario framing across different drivers) and their sectoral extensions (which interpreted the storylines and provided more detail in energy²², emissions²³, and land sectors²⁴). Our pathway narratives were also described consistent with FeliX structure and assumptions. For example, we described the trends in economy across our five scenarios in harmony with the original SSPs, but also in relation to parameters in the FeliX’s economy module, e.g., ‘capital elasticity of output’ and ‘labour force participation fraction’.

We developed the narratives of five pathways under five SSP-RCP combinations from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Projects (CMIP6)²¹ (Supplementary Table 1). Green Recovery (SSP 1 – RCP 2.6) depicts an inclusive and environmentally-friendly progress directly relating to the concept of sustainable development. Business As Usual (SSP 2 – RCP 4.5) is the continuation of past and current trajectories. Fragmented World (SSP 3 RCP 7.0) represents a conflicted world with weak global cooperation and high consumption and environmental footprints. A world of Inequality (SSP 4 – RCP 6.0) is featured with highly unequal human development investments with disparities in economic opportunities. Fossil-Fuelled Development (SSP 5 – RCP 8.5) is driven by rapid human and economic prosperity yet highly polluting and consumption driven. Similar to the original SSPs, our five pathway narratives were developed consistent with different degrees of challenges to mitigation (of the emissions from energy and land-use) and adaptation to climate change and their impact on the society^{25,26}. Four of these storylines (Green Recovery, Fragmented World, Inequality, and Fossil-Fuelled Development) represent a combination of high and low challenges to climate adaptation and mitigation while the fifth (Business As Usual) represents moderate challenges of both kind in a business-as-usual trajectory.

Identify the drivers of the pathway narratives in FeliX. We took three steps to identify the important pathway drivers in FeliX. The technical details of each step are elaborated as follows.

Selecting the initial list of candidate uncertain model parameters. We initially selected a list of uncertain model parameters (e.g., technological, emissions, economic) that can be related to socioeconomic, energy, land-use, and food and diet change drivers in the pathway narratives¹⁸. To make this initial list, we compared model parameters across its ten sectors (i.e., population, education, economy, energy, water, land, food and diet change, carbon cycle, climate, and biodiversity) against the list of pathway drivers and selected the uncertain model parameters that could meaningfully correspond to (or extend) these qualitative drivers. For example, we related the uncertain model

parameter about diet composition and diet change to ‘food consumption and diet change’ driver in the narratives. Conversely, we did not include the ‘impact of carbon on land fertility’ or ‘water withdrawal rate’ from the model in the initial list of candidate uncertain model parameters as they were related to a biophysical process or a sectoral area (e.g., water) which were not explicitly captured in our storylines. This selection process resulted in an initial list of 114 candidate uncertain model parameters available in Supplementary Table 2.

Screening the sensitivity of candidate uncertain model parameters. The listed uncertain model parameters can have different levels of influence on model behaviour, and therefore on the projections of the future scenarios with FeliX. Among the parameters, some may have only a trivial impact, therefore these should be identified and removed from the list of uncertain model parameters as their presence does not impact model projections. To analyse the importance of the candidate uncertain model parameters, we performed a series of global sensitivity analyses to prioritise the parameters based on their influence on future projections of the pathway narratives. The future projections of the storylines for global sensitivity analysis were across 20 control variables across nine sectors (i.e., population, economy, energy, water, carbon cycle, climate, biodiversity, land-use, diet change), equivalent to variables reported in the original database²⁷ of SSP projections (Supplementary Table 3). In the list of control variables, we only included radiative forcing from CO₂ emissions and did not include total radiative forcing as FeliX computes the former endogenously and uses other integrated assessment model projections (i.e., external data) for radiative forcing from emissions non-CO₂ gases.

Global sensitivity analysis computes the importance of each parameter in interaction with all other parameters. This multivariate analysis is suitable for the large number of highly uncertain parameters in the FeliX model, with a complex structure and nonlinear relationships. Among the reference global sensitivity analysis techniques²⁸, the Sobol technique²⁹ identifies each uncertain parameter’s contributions to non-linear, non-additive model output variance with multiple indices such as the total-order effect which shows the overall role of a parameter in an output (i.e., fraction of output variance related to the parameter and to its interactions with other parameters). Despite the good precision of Sobol total-order effect in prioritising model parameters, the technique is computationally intensive, especially in working with complex models. For example, Jaxa-Rozen & Kwakkel²⁸ showed that Sobol indices for a model with 19 parameters required at least 150,000 experiments (i.e., model evaluations) to stabilise. For FeliX with 114 uncertain parameters, we computed Sobol indices for more than 1,000,000 experiments, but the sensitivity indices did not converge yet. We therefore used Morris^{30,31} elementary effects instead. Morris is a well-established and suitable technique for screening and identifying unimportant parameters (i.e., factor fixing) from a large number of uncertain inputs in complex models with high computational costs. Several previous studies have showed the computational efficiency and the acceptability of Morris indices compared to other global sensitivity analysis techniques such as Sobol^{31,32}.

Morris relies on systematic sampling from uncertain parameters to generate a randomised one-factor-at-a-time ensemble of experiments. Using generated experiments, it computes a number of incremental ratios (i.e. elementary effects) which are averaged to measure the overall importance of a parameter. This demands at least a total evaluation of $r \times (k + 1)$ experiments, where r is the number of computed elementary effects and k is the number of parameters. The original Morris sensitivity indices are μ and σ , assessing the mean and standard deviation of the distribution of

elementary effects. The μ index represents the overall effect of the parameter on output and the σ index shows the magnitude of high-order effects because of non-linearity and interactions. Campolongo, et al.³¹, however, showed that the original Morris indices for ranking parameters can be unsatisfactory in non-monotonic types of models. They therefore improved Morris sampling and introduced a new index, μ^* , which can be sufficient on its own to provide a reliable ranking³¹ and that could acceptably estimate the Sobol total-order effect. The μ^* index can therefore be reliably used for screening important parameters (or parameters with negligible influence) in model projections under future scenarios. To perform Morris sensitivity analysis and compute μ^* , we used the SALib library³³ implementation of this technique, running through the EMA workbench³⁴ in Python.

We tested the sensitivity of 114 candidate uncertain model parameters (with their interactions). Given that the model generates timeseries data (1900-2100), we varied model parameters only from 2020 onwards. The sensitivity analysis process resulted in the ranking of candidate uncertain model parameters based on their influence across 20 control variables in 226,000 experiments (model evaluations). To ensure a stabilised ranking of parameters across all indicators, we documented the sensitivity index of all candidate parameters across all control variables for different size of experiments (model evaluations) up to the maximum of 565,000 model evaluations. We analysed the convergence of the sensitivity index of the candidate parameters per each control variable across different size of experiments to make sure that the ranking remains stable (Supplementary Figure 1). We computed μ^* over time (2030, 2050, 2100). Given that the sensitivities of model parameters did not vary significantly over time, we selected sensitivities to the 2100 projection as our reference (Supplementary Figure 2). This was also consistent with the SSP assumptions that the emergence of pathway drivers should happen in long-term and the full extent of patterns (e.g., minimum climate impacts, the stabilisation of population, bending of biodiversity loss) is realised by 2100 (and not earlier, e.g., 2050). Supplementary Figure 3 show the Morris sensitivity index of μ^* , normalised based on Min-Max Feature scaling³⁵, in other timesteps of 2030 and 2050.

Identifying influential uncertain model parameters from sensitivity analysis results. While Morris sensitivity analysis, as a screening (prioritising) technique, helped in ranking all of the 114 parameters, it did not apply any selection to limit the initial list of uncertain model parameters. To identify influential parameters from the ranking results, a cut-off value is usually selected for the sensitivity index. However, *a priori* selection of the cut-off value is often challenging as sensitivity threshold can vary significantly from one control variable to another. It is even more complex in this model with a large number of parameters control variables. Moreover, a fixed cut-off value is not informative in selecting among parameters that are close to the cut-off value. For example, if 0.70 is the cut-off value, the inclusion or exclusion of two parameters with sensitivity index of 0.701 and 0.699 could have very similar impact on control variable. Therefore, the inclusion of one and exclusion of the other becomes too biased to our selected threshold. Any *a priori* assignment of the cut-off value in a subjective manner (e.g., sensitivity index higher than a fixed value or a fixed top number of parameters) can lead to either the inclusion of a large set of parameters, some of which with negligible effects that only cause an over-parametrisation of the model (when the cut-off value is generous to accept low sensitivity) or to the exclusion of some important parameters that could potentially have significant effects for making more robust projections (when the cut-off value is too strict and only accepts very high sensitivity).

We selected important model parameters by systematically evaluating the consequences of the inclusion and exclusion of various parameters across control variables before making any subjective decision about the cut-off value as also described in Methods (main text). We iterated over the parameter lists and generated experiments with Latin Hypercube Sampling in three different sets per control variable. Set 1 was based on Latin Hypercube sampling across all top 20 most important parameters identified through the global sensitivity analysis. Set 2 included sampling across the top n important parameters from the global sensitivity analysis results where the top n parameters could vary in their uncertainty range while other parameters were fixed to their default reference value. Set 3 included sampling across the top n important parameters fixed with their default reference value while varying other parameters within their uncertainty range. For each control variable, we started from $n = 1$ to generate Sets 1, 2, and 3 (i.e., the first top important parameter is capable of generating most of variations in each output indicator that we observed in Set 1). We generated the three Sets each with 2000 model evaluations and computed the correlation coefficient between Sets 1 and 2 and between Sets 1 and 3. We increased $n = n + 1$ until $n = N$ where we achieved at least 99% correlation between Sets 1 and 2, that is when the top N parameters can generate at least 99% of variations equivalent to the variation of all parameters together in each control variable ($3 \text{ sets} \times 2000 \text{ evaluations} \times N \text{ parameters} \times 20 \text{ control variable} = 2,400,000 \text{ model evaluations in total}$). While we did not include the correlation between Sets 1 and 3 in deciding about the top parameters, we visually checked this correlation to confirm that the interactions of the non-top parameters did not lead to a significant variance. This process resulted in a list of 60 influential uncertain parameters (Supplementary Table 4). The summary of correlation improvement between the three sets in the final number of n top-ranked uncertain parameters is available in Supplementary Figure 4.

The identified influential uncertain model parameters were used as FeliX's pathway drivers in the next steps. The identified drivers were diverse enough to capture influential global change in relation to demographic and educational development, economic growth, energy and climate, land-use, and diet change, closely related to the sustainable development goals. Substantial variations were found among the influence of these drivers where the demographic (e.g., fertility rate), education, economic (e.g., capital elasticity of the economy), and lifestyle (energy demand and food diet) were among the most influential drivers across all control variables. This implied that ensuring a sustainable future requires socioeconomic development that improve human wellbeing while changing behavioural and consumption patterns to preserve the planet's stability. It also resonated with the underpinning assumption of socioeconomic factors that drive the climate change scenarios and the finding of other integrated system projections.

Calibrate FeliX's drivers under the pathway narratives. The shared socioeconomic pathways have been implemented in different integrated assessment models (e.g., GCAM, IMAGE) to a different extent aligned with the model structure, assumptions, and their required input parameter, and based on their model's strengths and weaknesses. Despite sharing the key characteristics, some differences still remained in the quantification of the shared socioeconomic pathways across models, and different structures and assumptions across IAMs and with FeliX do not allow for a precise harmonisation of the SSP quantification. A varied yet internally consistent quantification across IAMs is useful as it generates alternative results leading to a robust understanding of the future developments through comparing between different projections. We therefore used the influential uncertain model parameters (identified through sensitivity analysis) as the pathway drivers in FeliX. We then calibrated and quantified these model parameters under the assumption of each narrative.

To calibrate FeliX under the assumption of each narrative, we firstly calibrated the model with the formally quantified population, economic growth, and educational attainment as the basic socioeconomic elements of shared socioeconomic pathways. We used the demographic and economic quantification of socioeconomic elements developed by Samir and Lutz³⁶ (for population and education) and Dellink *et al.*³⁷ (for GDP) as presented in Supplementary Figure 5. For the purpose of this article, we used aggregated data at the global level (average of low- and high-income countries). For population and educational attainment, we used the projection of the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis and for GDP we used the projection from the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). We used Vensim software's calibration to estimate the value of uncertain model parameters as described in Methods (main text). See Code and Data Availability (main text) for implementation.

To calibrate scenario drivers related to energy and climate, land, and food and diet, we firstly identified which uncertain model parameter(s) in FeliX (Supplementary Table 4) are related to each pathway driver in the narratives. In other words, we identified through which uncertain parameter(s) we can model the impacts of each pathway driver. We then calibrated the relevant model parameters in harmony with the assumptions of the pathway narratives. For example, to model the differences in energy demand across scenario narratives, we calibrated three FeliX's parameters related to the maximum reference energy demand per capita (as a cap to limit the growth of energy demand within a reasonable range), the reference market share for different energy sources, and the price elasticity of demand (to compute the effect of price competitiveness on reference market share). To model energy technology advances in the narratives, we calibrated the productivity and efficiency of fossil fuel and renewable energy technologies as parameters related to technology improvement in FeliX. We also calibrated money available to improve energy technology through a fraction of revenue from fossil fuels that are invested in technology development. Variation in the state of energy production across the narratives was modelled in FeliX through calibrating the change in the size resources for fossil fuels (as a result of annual growth in the size of discovered resources with new discovery and exploration technologies) and the variation in the reference cost of energy production from renewable sources. Environmental concerns in energy production in the narratives were modelled through the use of carbon captured and storage technology and the desired (upper limit) acceptable total carbon emission from fossil fuels. To model variation in land-use change, we calibrated the rate and delay in forest to agricultural lands conversion where higher rate and shorter delay implied weak regulations to limit deforestation. Land-use change was also modelled through the expansion of built-up areas as a result of the impact of GDP growth (prosperity) on urbanisation. Variation in land-use productivity growth was captured in FeliX through calibrating the reference productivity in tons of meat yield (per ha) of grassland as well as the reference impact of technology advancement on agricultural land fertility. We modelled variation in food consumption by calibrating a waste fraction multiplier in animal and plant-based foods as well as daily average calorie intake (the higher food waste and calorie intake, the more food consumption). The variation in environmental impacts of food consumptions was also calibrated in FeliX through a shift in diet. The diet change was modelled as a categorical parameter which can vary between the five discrete groups of diet compositions rather (see Eker *et al.*⁴ for the details of each diet composition). Diet composition 1 (Sustainable) was when meat-eaters become flexitarian (limited animal-based foods) and vegetarians eat vegan (high plant-based foods). Diet composition 2 (relatively sustainable) was when meat-eaters

adopt a healthy diet (moderate animal-based foods and high plant-based foods) and vegetarians eat reference vegetarian diet. Diet composition 3 (relatively sustainable) was meat-eaters eat healthy diet and vegetarians eat a vegan diet. Diet composition 4 (slightly better than status quo) was when everyone (meat-eaters and vegetarians) is flexitarian (a mix of animal-based and plant-based foods), and therefore there is only a slight improvement from the current situation, but still on the same trends. Diet composition 5 (status quo) was when everyone follows the current reference meat and vegetarian diets (high meat and moderate vegetable consumption). In addition to change in diet composition, we also calibrated normal fraction of shift between vegetarianism and meat consumption (two ways) as factors that determine the degree of impact that change in diet composition can propagate in the sector food.

Characterise and validate future pathways. We used the calibrated values of the drivers in FeliX under each narrative to project future developments across multiple sectors (Supplementary Table 3) that were already qualitatively described in the narratives. We assumed that the drivers of the narratives emerge from 2020, and the value of the modelled drivers gradually increases towards their quantified values over 10 to 15 years. We assumed that this emergence time (i.e., the time required for the changes to unfold) as a range to account for deep uncertainty and that it can vary from one model parameter to another (e.g., technological improvement in renewable energy sector may emerge faster than diet change). Considering a delay time was consistent with the implementations of the shared socioeconomic pathways in other major integrated assessment models³⁸.

The quantification of the shared socioeconomic pathways in FeliX were also prone to deep uncertainties given that several equally valid quantification of the narratives can be assumed for model uncertain parameter. To account for the uncertainty in quantification, we assumed a range between 5% to 15% variations in the value of quantified model uncertain parameter and generated an ensemble of projections under each pathway rather than a single projection.

To validate FeliX projections under each scenarios, we compared them against the projections of the shared socioeconomic pathways by other research organisations (e.g., OECD³⁷, IIASA³⁶, PIK³⁹, and NCAR⁴⁰) or other integrated assessment models (i.e., IMAGE^{38,41}, MESSAGE-GLOBIOM^{42,43}, AIM⁴⁴, GCAM⁴⁵, REMIND-MAGPIE⁴⁶) across the control variables. FeliX vs. other model projections in some selected control variables are available in Extended Data Figure 4 and the projections in the rest of variables are in Supplementary Figure 6.

Supplementary Methods 3: SDG implementation

The United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development^{47,48}, adopted by all countries in 2015, outlines a path to 2030 with an intention to leave no one behind. It represents shared global aspirations for an inclusive and equitable development that can manage the social, physical, and ecological elements of the human-Earth systems in the Anthropocene. The 2030 Agenda calls for a comprehensive approach for “transforming the world” and achieving “the future we want” through meeting 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and 169 targets. The goals and targets are exhaustive enough to promote the welfare of the society while at the same time avoiding the transgression of planetary boundaries^{49,50}.

We implemented the 2030 agenda through a list of selected indicators with quantified targets and by measuring the progress towards achieving these targets (Methods). The indicators were selected from multiple official resources based on four criteria (Methods and Extended Data Figure 3): high applicability to the SDG framework, high model

credibility in projecting the indicator value, the availability of meaningful targets for measuring the progress towards each indicator. Measuring progress towards the indicators required specifying target levels consistent with different global ambitions and as the fit-for-purpose of highly ambitious targets is questioned for the post-pandemic age. Owing to the large uncertainty involved and the heterogeneity of resources available between countries, we defined three ambitious, moderate, and weak target levels. See Methods (main text) for the description the indicator selection and the target setting process, Extended Data Table 2 for the description of each indicator and the quantified target levels, Supplementary Table 5 for the justification of the target setting methods, and Supplementary Equations 1 to 36 for the methodology used for computing each indicator.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1. The narratives of future pathways framed by the five SSPs-RCPs. The narratives were used to guide qualitative and quantitative assumptions to the FeliX model.

Green Recovery	Business As Usual	Fragmented World	Inequality	Fossil-Fuelled Development
Population growth³⁶				
<i>Trend</i>				
Low population growth.	Moderate population growth.	High population growth.	Moderate population growth.	Low population growth.
<i>Narrative</i>				
Investments in human capital and education levels along with fast technological progress facilitate a demographic transition in currently high fertility countries towards a relatively low population. At the same time, the prosperous economic condition and healthy lifestyle increase the average life expectancy of the population, especially in low-income, developing countries.	Population growth is generally at a moderate level, with a faster growth in low-income countries, slowing population growth in middle-income countries, and very limited or aging population growth in more developed, high-income countries.	Limited education opportunities and a very slow economy induce a fast population growth, especially in developing countries when the socioeconomic conditions are worsening. At the same time, life expectancy in developing countries is short which to some extent can balance the high fertility, but it is not large enough to slow down the population growth. There is also a transition to more male babies than the females given the deliberate infant gender choice in low income countries ⁵¹ .	A general economic uncertainty in developed countries results in relatively low fertility and low population growth, and a moderate life expectancy. The low-income countries, however, experience high population growth due to the limited education and low life expectancy due to poor socioeconomic conditions. Same to SSP 3, there is a transition to more male babies than the females in low income countries.	Global population peaks and declines due to slowing of fertility rate in developing countries resulted from investment in education, health, and economic prosperity. In high-income countries, fertility can be above replacement due to optimistic economic futures.
Educational attainment³⁶				
<i>Trend</i>				
Low number of primary and secondary graduates but high number of tertiary graduates.	Moderate number of primary, secondary, and tertiary graduates.	High number of primary and secondary graduates but low number of tertiary graduates.	High number of primary and secondary graduates but relatively low number of tertiary graduates.	Low number of primary and secondary graduates but high number of tertiary graduates.
<i>Narrative</i>				
Universal access to primary and secondary and promoting higher education levels are achieved across all countries, especially in low-income countries, leading to poverty reduction and improvement of gender inequality.	Some progress towards universal education is achieved, but the investments are not high enough to reduce the population growth in low-income countries.	Very limited investments in education, especially in tertiary education, leads to poor populations in low-income countries with limited economic opportunities, working as a vicious cycle worsening gender inequality and increasing the population growth.	Investment on education in developing countries focusing on developing human capital based on small, highly educated elite at the expense of the broader public education.	Education and consequently poverty are significantly improved with the support of development policies that eventually aim to accelerate human capital development. Resources for.
Economic growth^{37,52}				
<i>Trend</i>				
Relatively high economic growth.	Moderate economic growth.	Low economic growth.	Relatively low economic growth.	High economic growth.
<i>Narrative</i>				
Fast economic growth is experienced across all countries (especially developing countries), although the economic development is tempered over time by achieving a balanced growth among well-being, equity, and sustainability.	Economic growth is moderate in general, following its historical patterns, with emerging economies experiencing a fast and a slowdown progress as their economies mature, low-income countries experiencing a relatively high growth, and high-income countries continuing to progress moderately	Limited international cooperation, low investments in education (and therefore limited training of skilled labour force) and in technology R&D result in a very slow economic growth with high inequalities across and within countries where the wealth is distributed unevenly.	The economy within and across countries works based on a high-tech, knowledge-based sector for highly educated labour force, and a low-tech, labour-intensive sector for a major part of the global population. This results in high- to middle-income (developed) countries to experience a moderate economic growth while low-income developing countries lag behind.	The globalised economies supported by a high level of international trade and cooperation result in a fast economic growth among countries. However, the growth is so much focused on consumerism and resource-intensive consumption.

Continued.

Energy demand and market share of renewable and fossil fuels^{18,22}

Trend

<p>Low energy demand. High, relatively high, and moderate market share for solar, biomass, and wind. Low market share for all fossil energies.</p>	<p>Relatively high energy demand. Relatively high, low, and high market share for solar, biomass, and wind. Moderate, moderate, and high market share for coal, gas, and oil.</p>	<p>Moderate energy demand. Low, high, and low market share for solar, biomass, and wind. Relatively high, relatively low, and moderate market share for coal, gas, and oil.</p>	<p>Moderate energy demand. Moderate market share for solar, biomass, and wind. Relatively low, low, and moderate market share for coal, gas, and oil.</p>	<p>High energy demand. Relatively high, low, and relatively high market share for solar, biomass, and wind. Relatively high, high, and high market share for coal, gas, and oil.</p>
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Narrative

<p>Fast economic growth along with city development increases the overall energy use of the population. However, environmental consciousness and sustainable development goals along with the efficient end-use technologies lead to a transition to low energy intensity of services. This creates a high desire to adopt non-bio renewable energies (wind and solar) in response to their steeped cost reduction (high price elasticity) resulted from technological progress and low desire to respond to use fossil energy, even with a very low price. The price elasticity of demand to biomass remain at a moderate level (less than wind and solar) due to concerns about its environmental impacts on land. A sustainable development with rapid economic growth and fast urbanisation across the world, especially in developing, low-income countries creates political determinism / market interest to rapidly phase out fossil fuel use.</p>	<p>Service demand levels are between SSP 1 and SSP 5 on a per capita level and energy intensity of services is moderate across all end-use sectors. While significant progress with solving the energy access and moving away from fossil fuels is achieved, some issues persist which keep the traditional fuel use at its current trajectory.</p>	<p>Because of relatively poor economic development, the maximum demand for energy services is limited. However, because of low environmental standards, poorly performing public infrastructure, and ineffective regulation, the energy intensity of services is medium to high leading to a medium to high final demand, and high price elasticity of demand for fossil energy (more desire to buy fossil fuel given that their price remains at an affordable level) and low price elasticity for renewable energy (no desire for renewable given that their technology development and price reduction are very slow), except for biomass. Given the slow economic development and limited technology advancement, a continued reliance on traditional fuels especially in low-income with large rural communities is unavoidable. Fossil market share is higher than renewables as there is no other practical alternative for fossil fuels.</p>	<p>High-income countries show a modest per capita energy service demand because of a divided society in which the majority has modest incomes, but more importantly in response to strong regulation (energy taxes). The latter also lead to incentives for reaching low energy intensity of services fuelled by (non-biomass) renewable energies. In contrast, the desire for meeting the energy demand from (non-biomass) renewable sources is low in low-income countries while there is more preference for fossil energy and biomass. Similar to SSP3, poor economic development in low-income countries limits maximum demand for energy services per capita. However, inefficient technologies along with high population leads to moderate final energy demand. Countries with a large population of low-income communities remain highly dependent on fossil fuel, given the divided income distributions (high market share for fossil fuels). However, developed, high-income countries have more interest and resource to transition from fossil fuels in their market.</p>	<p>The general preference for status consumption in urban sprawl in combination with prosperous economic development creates a lifestyle with high-energy service demand levels. Despite fast technological change, the market response to price change of renewable and fossil energies is relatively lower and higher than SSP 1. Despite fast economic development, the reliance on fossil fuel as the cheap source of energy remains much higher than SSP 1 in all countries (higher market share for fossil fuels).</p>
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Continued.

Energy technology advances (fossil fuels recovery and exploration technology development and renewable technology investment and efficiency)^{18,22}

<i>Trend</i>				
Fast renewable energy technology improvement, and limited fossil energy technology improvement (both efficiency and investment).	Moderate renewable and fossil energy technology improvement (both efficiency and investment).	Slow renewable and fossil energy technology improvement (both efficiency and investment).	Relatively slow renewable and fossil energy technology improvement (both efficiency and investment).	Moderate renewable energy technology improvement and fast fossil technology improvement (both efficiency and investment).
<i>Narrative</i>				
In a world with rapid technological change toward environmentally friendly processes, wind and solar energy technologies improve rapidly. The effectiveness of investments on fossil energy technologies is however moderate due to strict environmental regulations. Renewable energies especially solar which is experiencing a rapid growth (and is not like wind, close to its maximum capacity) have a high social acceptability (e.g., more land availability for solar technologies installation). However, all fossil energy technologies experience low social acceptance leading to less investment of the revenue achieved from fossil energies in the improvement of same fossil sector and long delay for approving intended investment (due to environmental regulations).	All technologies develop at a moderate rate and along their past trajectories. The investment and social acceptability of energy technologies are at a moderate level too.	With slow economic growth and low investments in technology R&D, technological changes of fossil and renewable technologies are slow throughout the world. Due to the dominance of local energy security goals and less concerns over global environmental issues, social acceptance for investment in fossil energy is high. However, renewable energies such as solar become less socially acceptable because of their limited costs reduction and technological advancement (e.g., facing more challenges in acquiring land for solar installation).	Technological development is fast for wind and solar in high-income countries and slow in low-income regions due to slower economic growth. The effectiveness of investment in fossil fuels remains at a moderate level in all countries. Social acceptance regarding energy sector (fossil and renewable) investments is generally higher in low-income countries due to their poor energy access condition and vulnerability to resource scarcity. Medium- to high-income countries also have a similar social acceptance for renewables, but fossil energy social acceptance remains weak due to presence of price competitive renewable alternatives. The delay in fossil investment in both country groups is high (in low-income regions due to ineffective regulations and the limitation on availability of domestic investors).	Fast technological development enhances the effectiveness and productivity of investment in fossil energy. There is modest but continued progress in wind and solar technologies due to the rapid economic growth and the expansion of renewable energy-related industries. Because of the strong preference for rapid conventional development, the world depends significantly on fossil energy and does not actively invest in alternative energy sources. This leads to high social acceptance for investment in fossil energy technologies low social acceptance for renewable energy.

Investment in fossil fuels and their resource availability, renewable production cost reduction, limit on emissions from fossil fuels^{18,22}

<i>Trend</i>				
High, relatively high, and moderate solar, biomass, and wind energy production. Low energy production for all fossil fuels. Low emissions and radiative forcing.	Relatively high, low, and high solar, biomass, and wind energy production. Moderate, moderate, and high coal, gas, and oil energy production. Relatively high emissions and radiative forcing.	Low, high, and low solar, biomass, and wind energy production. Relatively high, relatively low, and moderate coal, gas, and oil energy production. Relatively high emissions and radiative forcing.	Moderate solar, biomass, and wind energy production. Relatively low, low, and moderate coal, gas, and oil energy production. Moderate emissions and relatively high radiative forcing.	Relatively high, low, and relatively high solar, biomass, and wind energy production. Relatively high, high, and high coal, gas, and oil energy production. High emissions and radiative forcing.
<i>Narrative</i>				
Fast technological development and the strong acceptability of renewable energies lead to low production cost for renewable energies. In addition, tight policies on emissions from fossil fuels limit the production and discovery of fossil fuels, leading to a low availability of fossil fuel resources.	The availability of fossil fuels, emissions reduction, and the cost reduction in renewable energy production follow a business-as-usual trajectory.	There is a high challenge to mitigation (less than SSP 5) because of high availability of fossil fuels. However, technological progress for fossil energy technologies is less and therefore the potential for low cost recovery and exploration of fossil fuels remains less than SSP 5.	Fossil fuels availability is slightly higher than in SSP 1 and the unit cost of exploration is slightly lower. Therefore, due to more availability of fossil energy, the emissions remain at relatively moderate levels (compared to SSP 1). Renewable energy technologies are deployed at low costs throughout the world as multinational energy corporations co-invest in R&D and cost reduction as their hedging strategy against resource scarcity.	There is a high challenge to mitigation, resulted from a very high availability of fossil fuels, no significant reduction (compared to SSP 2) in renewable energy costs, and consequently, a higher acceptable baseline for emissions from fossil energy sector.

Continued.

Land-use change^{18,24,40}

Trends*Trend*

Low land cover built-up area. Deforestation at a slow rate and the expansion of cropland and pasture land at a slow rate.

Relatively low land cover built-up area. Deforestation at a moderate rate and the expansion of cropland and pasture land at a moderate rate too.

Low land cover built-up area. Deforestation at a high rate and the expansion of cropland and pasture land at a high rate too.

Relatively low land cover built-up area. Deforestation at a moderate rate and the expansion of cropland and pasture land at a moderate rate too.

High land cover built-up area. Deforestation at a relatively slow rate and the expansion of cropland and pasture land at a relatively slow rate too.

Narrative

Along with economic development and increase in GDP across all countries, the rural population is attracted to urban centres. Urbanisation (shared/concentrated resources) also grows fast for environmental reasons. Thus, with cities as attractive destinations, the growth of GWP correlates with the acquisition of more lands for city expansion, while minimising the environmental impacts. Land use is strongly regulated. As a result, the deforestation rates are strongly reduced over time. This would be more in low-income, developing countries. The expansion of cropland and pasture land also happens at a slow rate due to low population growth and a transition to sustainable diets.

All countries experience an extension of current trends in urbanisation, with the central urbanization pathway in various forms and patterns depending on their conditions and resources. While high-income countries continue their urban expansion trajectory, other medium- and low-income (developing) countries follow the historical urbanisation experiences of the more developed countries. Land use change is incompletely regulated. As a result, the deforestation continues, but with a gradual decline over time. Cropland and pasture land growth at a moderate rate due to business as usual population growth and food consumption.

Slow GDP growth along with strict measures on international migration, and poor urban planning make cities unattractive. The rapid population growth along with slow socioeconomic development and environmental degradation also limit the mobility of the poor rural population. Thus, developments have limited impact on the expansion of cities and the acquisition of required lands for urban and industrial activities. With little regulation in place, there is continued deforestation because of rapid agricultural expansion driven by regional rivalry and domestic food security, and regional conflicts. Cropland and pasture land expand fast to meet the increasing food demand in a world with a fast growing population.

Cities in high-income countries with high living standards become attractive for global migration. However, the aging of the population in high-income countries limit internal rural-to-urban migration at a moderate level, contributing to a slow city expansion. Low-income countries with their rapidly growing rural populations, exposed by limited areas of arable land and job availability due to large-scale mechanised farming by international agricultural firms, experience a significant migration to urban areas in the hope of better opportunities. Land use is highly regulated in high- and middle-income countries, but deforestation still occurs in poor countries. Cropland and pasture land expand to meet the global food demand, they have a moderate expansion rate.

Many large-scale engineering projects for the expansion of cities take place, supported by rapid technological progress and fast economic growth. However, the urban development is more in form of extensive man-made environments leading to urban sprawl with rather comfortable living conditions with high environmental footprints. Land use change is incompletely regulated. Thus, deforestation continues, but at a slowly declining rate over time. Low population and therefore less demand for food results in the expansion of cropland and pasture land at a slower rate compared to business as usual (but higher than SSP 1)

Land productivity growth^{18,24}

Trend

High crops and livestock yield.

Moderate crops and livestock yield.

Low crops and livestock yield.

Relatively low crops and livestock yield.

Relatively high crops and livestock yield.

Narrative

Rapid improvement of the environmentally-friendly technologies in the land sector results in high crops and livestock yield, especially in low- and medium-income countries, enabling them to catch up faster with high-income countries.

Crops and livestock yield decline slowly over time, but it gradually improves in low-income countries, which enable them to catch up with developed regions.

Limited international collaborations for technology transfer in low-income countries, slow economic growth and availability of resources and lack of required knowledge result in a strong decline in crops and livestock yield over time.

High-income countries supported by large-scale industrial farming can realise high crops and livestock yield whereas low-income countries with local and inefficient farming practices remain relatively unproductive in agriculture.

Crops and livestock yield id rapidly increasing due to advancement of technology and enhanced production systems.

Food waste, food consumption, diet change⁴

Trend

Low waste, low plant foods consumption, low animal foods consumption, more sustainable diets.

Waste at the current level, moderate plant and animal foods consumption, the global diet follows the status quo (more meat, less vegetables).

Relatively high waste, moderate plant and animal foods consumption, the global diet follows the status quo (more meat, less vegetables).

Relatively low waste, moderate plant and animal foods consumption, the global diet follows may slightly to towards the less meat, more vegetables.

High waste, high plant and animal foods consumption, the global diet follows the status quo (more meat, less vegetables).

Narrative

With a universal education, especially at tertiary levels and low population growth, healthy diets with low animal-calorie shares prevail and the food waste drops significantly, driven by environmental consciousness.

Caloric consumption and animal calorie shares converge slowly towards high levels and food waste remains relatively unchanged.

With a great increase in population, poor economic development, and minimum access to education, unhealthy diets with high animal shares and high food waste prevail.

Caloric consumption and animal calorie shares converge towards medium levels, while the shift to healthy diets is stronger in high-income countries because of higher education level and improved lifestyle.

High-income countries experience meat-rich and unhealthy diets and high waste prevail resulted from rapid economic growth and consumerism.

Continued.

Climate mitigation policy assumptions

Trend

RCP 2.6 - Low challenges to mitigation.

RCP 4.5 - Medium mitigation challenges.

RCP 7.0 Significant challenges to mitigation.

RCP 6.0 - Low challenges to mitigation.

RCP 8.5 - High mitigation challenges.

Narrative

As an indicative scenario for low-range emissions with the highest potential for mitigation facilitated by technology advances and high level of global cooperation, we assumed carbon pricing for fossil fuel unit cost of production with a linearly increasing (global average) trajectory (reaching ~\$450 per tCO₂ by 2100) and land-based mitigations (reaching zero emissions from land use by 2060). We also assumed carbon capture and storage for reducing emissions from fossil fuels and from bioenergy (BECCS). To indicate less global cooperation in adopting climate policies, all measures were implemented by 2025. For other greenhouse gases that were not modelled endogenously in FeliX, we calibrated the model under the green recovery consistent with the lowest forcing level of 2.6 W m².

With medium mitigation challenges, we assumed slightly lower carbon price (reaching ~\$300 per tCO₂ by 2100) compared to Green Recovery, lower adoption of carbon capture and storage for reducing emissions from fossil fuels and also from bioenergy (BECCS), and also lower land-based mitigations (reaching 1.6 Gt CO₂ from land use by 2100). To indicate less global cooperation in adopting climate policies, all measures were implemented by 2040, later than the green recovery. For other gases, we calibrated the model consistent with 4.5 W m² forcing level.

With significant challenges to mitigation (and also with little global cooperation in the former), we did not assume the impacts of global level climate policies for carbon emissions in FeliX. For other gases, we calibrated the model consistent with 7.0 W m² forcing level.

Similar to Business As Usual, with medium mitigation challenges, we assumed slightly lower carbon price (reaching ~\$300 per tCO₂ by 2100) compared to Green Recovery, lower adoption of carbon capture and storage for reducing emissions from fossil fuels and also from bioenergy (BECCS), and also lower land-based mitigations (reaching 1.6 Gt CO₂ from land use by 2100). For other gases, we calibrated the model consistent with 6.0 W m² forcing level.

Similar to Fragmented World, with significant challenges to mitigation (and also with little global cooperation in the former), we did not assume the impacts of global level climate policies for carbon emissions in FeliX. For other gases, we calibrated the model consistent with 8.5 W m² forcing level.

Supplementary Table 2. The list of candidate uncertain model parameters identified in relation to pathway drivers.

See the Supplementary_Tables_2_4_5.xlsx file.

Supplementary Table 3. Control variables used in analysing the sensitivity of future projections to the candidate uncertain model parameters. The variables and their units were selected based on the corresponding projections in the original SSP database²⁷.

Sector	Indicator	Unit
Socioeconomic	Total Population	million
	Total Primary Education Graduates	million
	Total Secondary Education Graduates	million
	Total Tertiary Education Graduates	million
	GWP per Capita	\$1000/(person*year)
Energy and climate	Energy Demand	EJ/year
	Solar Energy Production	EJ/year
	Wind Energy Production	EJ/year
	Biomass Energy Production	EJ/year
	Oil Production	EJ/year
	Gas Production	EJ/year
	Coal Production	EJ/year
	Total CO ₂ Emissions	million ton CO ₂ /year
	CO ₂ Radiative Forcing	w/m ²
	Land	Total Croplands
Forest Land		million ha
Pasture Land		million ha
Urban Industrial Land		million ha
Food and diet	Nonenergy Crops Production	million ton DM/year
	Livestock Production	million ton DM/year

Supplementary Table 4. The list of important uncertain model parameters and their quantification under future pathways.

See the Supplementary_Tables_2_4_5.xlsx file.

Supplementary Table 5. The description of indicators and the justification of the targets set on each indicator.

See the Supplementary_Tables_2_4_5.xlsx file.

Supplementary Equations

Cereal Yield is computed as in Equation 1.

$$CY(t) = \frac{PR_{grains}(t) \times AH_{grains}(t)}{AH_{grains}(t)} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where CY is the annual cereal production rate per hectare of harvested croplands dedicated to grains production ($\text{kg year}^{-1}\text{ha}^{-1}$), PR is crop yield per each category of crops ($\text{ton ha}^{-1}\text{year}^{-1}$), which is a function of the effects of fertiliser application, managerial practices, water withdrawal, and climate change on agriculture land fertility, and AH is the harvest area (ha).

Vegetal Food supply is computed as in Equation 2.

$$FS_{vegetal}(t) = \frac{\sum_{f \in PF} TFS_f(t) \times uc}{P(t) \times dy} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

Where $FP_{vegetal}$ is the total annual production of plant products per person per day, $TFS_f(t)$ is the total supply of calories for food type f , PF is the plant food categories including pulses, grains, vegetable, fruits, roots, and other plant products (oil crops, sugar crops and nuts), $P(t)$ is the total population size at each year, uc denotes the unit conversion factor (Mkcal to kcal), and dy is the number of days in a year.

Animal Food supply is computed as in Equation 3.

$$FS_{animal}(t) = \frac{\sum_{f \in AF} TFS_f(t) \times uc}{P(t) \times dy} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

Where FP_{animal} is the total annual production of animal food products (excluding seafoods) per person per day, $TFS_f(t)$ is the total supply of calories for food type f , AF is the animal-based food products including pasture-based meat (beef, sheep and goat) and crop-based meat (poultry and pork), eggs and dairy, $P(t)$ is the total population size at each year, uc denotes the unit conversion factor (Mkcal to kcal), and dy is the number of days in a year.

Total Food Supply is computed as in Equation 4.

$$FS_{total}(t) = FS_{vegetal}(t) + FS_{animal}(t)$$

Where FS_{total} is the total annual plant- and meat-based food production per person per day, $FS_{vegetal}$ is the total annual production of plant products per person per day, and FS_{animal} is the total annual production of animal food products (excluding seafoods) per person per day.

Ratio of Agricultural Lands to Total Lands is computed as in Equation 5.

$$RL_a(t) = \frac{LDR_a(t) + LC_{fa}(t) - LC_{au}(t) - LC_{af}(t) - LE_a(t)}{L_{total}(t)} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

Where RL is the ratio of land allocated to a specific land-use to total available lands, a denotes agricultural land-use (i.e., permanent crops, permanent meadows and pastures, arable lands), and LDR_a is the agricultural land development rate, LC_{fa} is deforestation to agricultural land, LC_{au} is agricultural land conversion rate to urban land, LC_{af} is forestation from agricultural land, LE_a is agricultural land erosion rate, L_{total} is total area of land for all types of land-uses (i.e., agricultural, forest, urban and industrial, and other land-uses).

Pasture Land Indicator is computed as in Equation 6.

$$L_p(t) = L_a(t) \times RAL_p \times uc \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

Where L_p is the area of land allocated to permanent pastures and meadows (million ha), L_a is total area of land for agricultural land-uses, RAL_p is the percentage of meadows and pastures in agriculture lands, and uc denotes the unit conversion factor (million ha ha⁻¹).

Total Croplands Indicator is computed as in Equation 7.

$$L_c(t) = L_a(t) \times (RAL_{pcrops} + RAL_{arable}) \times uc \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

Where L_c is the area of land allocated to for energy and food (and feed) crops (million ha), L_a is total area of land for agricultural land-uses, RAL_{pcrops} is the permanent crops percentage of agriculture land, RAL_{arable} is the arable percentage of agriculture land, and uc denotes the unit conversion factor (million ha ha⁻¹).

Life Expectancy is computed as in Equation 8.

$$LE(t) = LE_{ref} \times LM_{food}(t) \times LM_{health}(t) \times LM_{climate}(t) \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

Where LE is the average life expectancy of the population (year), LE_{ref} is a referenced normal value for life expectancy and LMs are lifetime multiplier from food, health, and climate risk.

Human Development Index is computed as in Equation 9.

$$HDI(t) = HI(t)^{-3} \times II(t)^{-3} \times EI(t)^{-3} \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

Where HDI is the UNDP Human Development Index representing the achievement of income, health, education prosperity and its value represents human capabilities sustainable wellbeing (%), HI is the health index, II is the income index, and EI is the education index.

Mean Years of Schooling is computed as in Equation 10.

$$YS(t) = \frac{\sum_{e \in E} TY_e(t)}{\sum_{g \in G} \sum_{c \in C} P_{g,c}(t)} \quad \text{Equation 10}$$

Where YS is the average number of completed years of primary, secondary, and tertiary education (combined) of population (year), TY_e is total duration in the e level of education (person year), E denotes the three primary,

secondary, and tertiary levels of education, $P_{g,c}$ is the population size of gender g and age cohort c , G denotes both male and female genders, and C denotes age cohorts.

Population Age 25 to 34 with Tertiary Education is computed as in Equation 11.

$$PT(t) = \frac{\sum_{g \in G} \sum_{c \in C} TG_{g,c}(t)}{\sum_{g \in G} \sum_{c \in C} P_{g,c}(t)} \quad \text{Equation 11}$$

Where PT is the percentage of the population, aged between 25-34 years old, who have completed tertiary education, $TG_{g,c}$ is the number tertiary education graduates for gender g and age cohort c , G denotes both male and female genders, and C denotes age cohorts between 25 and 34.

Female to Male Enrollment in Tertiary Education is computed as in Equation 12.

$$FM_{tertiary}(t) = \frac{ERT_{female}(t)}{ERT_{male}(t)} \quad \text{Equation 12}$$

Where $FM_{tertiary}$ is the percentage of the female to male graduation rate from tertiary education, ERT_{female} is the graduation rate of female population from tertiary education, and ERT_{male} is the graduation rate of male population from tertiary education.

Share of Renewable Energy Supply is computed as in Equation 13.

$$SES_{renewable}(t) = \frac{\sum_{e \in ER} EP_e(t)}{EP_{total}(t)} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 13}$$

Where $SES_{renewable}$ is the percentage of renewable energy supply share in total energy production, EP_e is the energy production from source e , ER denotes the three biomass, solar, and wind renewable sources, and EP_{total} is total energy production from both fossil and renewable sources.

Share of Fossil Energy Supply is computed as in Equation 14.

$$SES_{fossil}(t) = \frac{\sum_{e \in EF} EP_e(t)}{EP_{total}(t)} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 14}$$

Where SES_{fossil} is the percentage of fossil energy supply share in total energy production, EP_e is the energy production from source e , EF denotes the three coal, oil, and gas fossil sources, and EP_{total} is total energy production from both fossil and renewable sources.

Solar Energy Production Indicator is computed as in Equation 15.

$$EP_{solar}(t) = \min\left(\frac{PEP_{solar}(t)}{ED_{solar}(t)}\right) \times uc \quad \text{Equation 15}$$

Where EP_{solar} is the energy production from solar (EJ year^{-1}), that is limited by PEP_{solar} which is possible energy production from solar (maximum capacity) based on sun radiation, solar conversion efficiency factor, and available installed capacity, ED_{solar} which is energy demand for solar based on solar market share from total demand. uc is also the unit conversion factor (EJ Mtoe^{-1}).

Wind Energy Production Indicator is computed as in Equation 16.

$$EP_{wind}(t) = \min\left(\frac{PEP_{wind}(t)}{ED_{wind}(t)}\right) \times uc \quad \text{Equation 16}$$

Where EP_{wind} is the energy production from wind (EJ year^{-1}), that is limited by PEP_{wind} which is possible energy production from wind (maximum capacity) based on average capacity per m^2 , a wind capacity factor multiplier, and wind installed capacity, ED_{wind} which is energy demand for wind based on its market share from total demand. uc is also the unit conversion factor (EJ Mtoe^{-1}).

Biomass Energy Production Indicator is computed as in Equation 17.

$$EP_{biomass}(t) = \min\left(\frac{PEP_{biomass}(t)}{ED_{biomass}(t)}\right) \times uc \quad \text{Equation 17}$$

Where $EP_{biomass}$ is the energy production from biomass (EJ year^{-1}), that is limited by $PEP_{biomass}$ which is possible energy production from biomass (maximum capacity), $ED_{biomass}$ which is energy demand for biomass based on its market share from total demand. uc is also the unit conversion factor (EJ Mtoe^{-1}).

Oil Production Indicator is computed as in Equation 18.

$$EP_{oil}(t) = \min\left(\frac{PEP_{oil}(t)}{ED_{oil}(t)}\right) \times uc \quad \text{Equation 18}$$

Where EP_{oil} the energy production from oil (EJ year^{-1}), that is limited by PEP_{oil} which is possible energy production from oil (maximum capacity) based on resource availability, investment, and technology improvement, ED_{oil} which is energy demand for oil based on its market share from total demand. uc is also the unit conversion factor (EJ Mtoe^{-1}).

Coal Production Indicator is computed as in Equation 19.

$$EP_{coal}(t) = \min\left(\frac{PEP_{coal}(t)}{ED_{coal}(t)}\right) \times uc \quad \text{Equation 19}$$

Where EP_{coal} is the energy production from coal (EJ year^{-1}), that is limited by PEP_{coal} which is possible energy production from coal (maximum capacity) based on resource availability, investment, and technology improvement, ED_{coal} which is energy demand for coal based on its market share from total demand. uc is also the unit conversion factor (EJ Mtoe^{-1}).

Gas Production Indicator is computed as in Equation 20.

$$EP_{gas}(t) = \min\left(\frac{PEP_{gas}(t)}{ED_{gas}(t)}\right) \times uc \quad \text{Equation 20}$$

Where EP_{gas} is the energy production from gas (EJ year⁻¹), that is limited by PEP_{gas} which is possible energy production from gas (maximum capacity) based on resource availability, investment, and technology improvement, ED_{gas} which is energy demand for gas based on its market share from total demand. uc is also the unit conversion factor (EJ Mtoe⁻¹).

Energy Intensity of GWP is computed as in Equation 21.

$$EI(t) = \frac{EP_{total}(t) \times uc}{GWP(t)} \quad \text{Equation 21}$$

Where EI is energy consumption per unit of GWP production (MJ \$⁻¹) indicating how much energy is used to produce one unit of economic output (lower ratio means that less energy is used to produce one unit of output), EP_{total} is the total energy production from both renewable and fossil resources, GWP is gross world product, and uc is the unit conversion factor (MJ Mtoe⁻¹).

GWP per Capita is computed as in Equation 22.

$$GWP(t) = REO(t) \times ME_{climate}(t) \times ME_{biodiversity}(t) \times uc \quad \text{Equation 22}$$

Where GWP is the gross world product (\$1000 person⁻¹ year⁻¹), REO is the reference economy output based on change in technology and capital, $ME_{climate}$ is the net climate change impact on economy, $ME_{biodiversity}$ is the impact of biodiversity on economy, and uc is the unit conversion factor (\$1000).

CO₂ Emissions per GWP is computed as in Equation 23.

$$EGWP(t) = \frac{CE_{fossil}(t) \times uc}{GWP(t)} \quad \text{Equation 23}$$

Where $EGWP$ is human-originated carbon dioxide emissions stemming from emissions the burning of fossil per GWP (kgCO₂ \$⁻¹), CE_{fossil} is the total CO₂ emissions from fossil energy, GWP is gross world product, and uc is the unit conversion factor (kg ton⁻¹).

Agro Food Nitrogen Production Footprint is computed as in Equation 24.

$$FEC_N(t) = \frac{(DR(t) + LR(t)) \times uc}{P(t)} \quad \text{Equation 24}$$

Where FEC_N is the Total reactive nitrogen per year per capita accumulated through commercial application in agriculture and application with manure (kg year⁻¹ person⁻¹), DR is the denitrification rate, LR is the leaching and runoff rate, uc is the unit conversion factor (kg ton⁻¹), and P is the total population size.

Nitrogen Fertilizer Use in Agriculture is computed as in Equation 25.

$$FU_N(t) = FU_{ref} \times FUM_{income}(t) \times FUM_{technology}(t) \times FUM_{land}(t) \times uc \quad \text{Equation 25}$$

Where FU_N is commercial nitrogen fertilizer application in agriculture (1000ton year⁻¹), FU_{ref} is the reference nitrogen consumption in 2010, FUM_{income} is the effect of income on fertilizer use, $FUM_{technology}$ is the effect of technology on fertilizer consumption, FUM_{land} is the effect of land availability on fertilizer use, and uc is the unit conversion factor (1000ton ton⁻¹).

Phosphorous Fertilizer Use in Agriculture is computed as in Equation 26.

$$FU_P(t) = CP_{agriculture}(t) \times cf \times uc \quad \text{Equation 26}$$

Where FU_P is commercial phosphorous fertilizer application in agriculture (1000ton year⁻¹), $CP_{agriculture}$ is the commercial P2O5 application for agriculture, cf is P2O5 to P conversion factor, and uc is the unit conversion factor (1000ton ton⁻¹).

Atmospheric Concentration CO₂ is computed as in Equation 27.

$$AC(t) = \frac{C(t)}{cf \times uc} \quad \text{Equation 27}$$

Where AC is atmospheric CO₂ concentration (ppm), C is carbon in atmosphere computed based on flux biomass to atmosphere, flux humus to atmosphere, and a total carbon emission-flux atmosphere to biomass-flux atmosphere to ocean, cf and uc are unit conversion factors.

Total CO₂ Emissions from AFOLU is computed as in Equation 28.

$$EC_{AFOLU}(t) = (C_{agriculture}(t) + C_{forest}(t)) \times uc \quad \text{Equation 28}$$

Where EC_{AFOLU} is the total CO₂ emissions from agriculture and land-use change (Gt CO₂ year⁻¹), $C_{agriculture}$ is total carbon emissions from agriculture, C_{forest} is total carbon emissions from forest land-use change, and uc is the unit conversion factor.

CO₂ Emissions from Fossil Energy is computed as in Equation 29.

$$EC_{fossil}(t) = C_{fossil}(t) \times uc \quad \text{Equation 29}$$

Where EC_{fossil} is total CO₂ emissions from fossil energy production (Gt CO₂ year⁻¹), C_{fossil} is total carbon emissions from fossil energy, and uc is the unit conversion factor.

Total CO₂ Emissions is computed as in Equation 30.

$$EC(t) = \frac{EC_{AFOLU}(t) + EC_{fossil}(t) + EC_{renewable}(t)}{P(t)} \quad \text{Equation 30}$$

Where EC is total CO₂ emissions, EC_{AFOLU} is the total CO₂ emissions from agriculture and land-use change, EC_{fossil} is the total CO₂ emissions from fossil energy, $EC_{renewable}$ is the total CO₂ emissions from renewable energy, and P is total population size.

Total Radiative Forcing is computed as in Equation 31.

$$RF_{total}(t) = RF_{CO_2}(t) + \sum_{g \in G} RF_g(t) \quad \text{Equation 31}$$

Where RF_{total} the difference between insolation (sunlight) absorbed by the Earth and energy radiated back to space from all greenhouse gases (W m⁻²), RF_{CO_2} is radiative forcing from CO₂ which is computed endogenously in the model, RF_g is radiative forcing from greenhouse gas g which is read in the model from external database, and G indicates CH₄, N₂O, HFC, and ‘others’.

CO₂ Radiative Forcing is computed as in Equation 32.

$$RF_{CO_2}(t) = RF_{coefficient} \times \ln \frac{C_{atmosphere}(t)}{C_{atmosphere}(t_{preindustrial})} \quad \text{Equation 32}$$

Where RF_{CO_2} is radiative forcing is resulted from CO₂ emissions (W m⁻²), $RF_{coefficient}$ is CO₂ radiative forcing coefficient, $C_{atmosphere}$ is carbon in atmosphere at any time, and $C_{atmosphere}(t_{preindustrial})$ is the preindustrial carbon in atmosphere.

Temperature Change from Preindustrial period is computed as in Equation 33.

$$TC(t) = \frac{H_{ao}(t)}{HC_{ao}(t)} \quad \text{Equation 33}$$

Where TC is the global annual mean temperature change from the pre-industrial time (degree C), H_{ao} is heat in atmosphere and upper ocean, and HC_{ao} is the atmospheric and upper ocean heat capacity.

Forest to Total Land Area is computed as in Equation 34.

$$RL_{forest}(t) = \frac{L_{forest}(t)}{L_{total}(t)} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 34}$$

Where RL_{forest} is the percentage of forest to total land areas, L_{forest} is the size of forest land areas, and L_{total} is the size of total available lands.

Forest Land Indicator is computed as in Equation 35.

$$L_{forest}(t) = (LC_{af}(t) + LC_{of}(t) - LC_{fa}(t) - LC_{fu}(t)) \times uc \quad \text{Equation 35}$$

Where L_{forest} is the size of forest land areas (million ha), LC_{af} forestation from agricultural lands, LC_{of} is forestation from other lands, LC_{fa} is deforestation to agricultural lands, LC_{fu} deforestation to urban lands, and uc is a unit conversion factor (million ha ha⁻¹).

Mean Species Abundance is computed as in Equation 36.

$$MSA(t) = SR(t) - SE(t) \quad \text{Equation 36}$$

Where MSA is the mean abundance of original species relative to their abundance in undisturbed ecosystems (%), SR is species regeneration rate, and SE is species extinction rate.

Adolescent Fertility Rate is computed as in Equation 37.

$$AFR(t) = \frac{AFF \times TF(t) \times 1000 \text{women}}{RL} \quad \text{Equation 37}$$

Where AFR is the number of births per 1,000 by women between the age of 15-19, AFF is the adolescent fertility fraction, $TF(t)$ is the total fertility which is a function of GDP and education, and RL is the adolescent reproductive lifetime.

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1. The convergence of parameter ranking and sensitivity index for the increasing number of experiments across 20 control variable. We only visualised the convergence of top 10 parameters which are the most sensitive in each control variable for better visibility.

Supplementary Figure 2. The sensitivity of model parameters in FeliX across 20 control variables in year 2100. Sensitivity is the normalised values of Morris index μ^* between 0 and 1. For each control variable, the most influential parameters are annotated with their importance rank.

Supplementary Figure 4. The gradual increase in the correlation coefficient between Sets 1 and 2 and the gradual reduction in the correlation coefficient between Sets 1 and 3 in the top n important parameters. Each marker correspond to one analysis (6000 model evaluation) conducted based on selecting the top n parameters and computing the correlation between Sets 1 and 2 and between Sets 1 and 3. The markers indicate the correction coefficients for each control variable (x-axis) in y-axis and the colour bar, starting from the very bottom marker with $n = 1$ and gradually increasing $n = n + 1$ until the accepted threshold on the correction coefficients is achieved at the very top marker ($n = N \leq 20$). The ideal is to maximise the correlation coefficient Set1 – Set2 (y-axis) while minimising correlation coefficient Set 1 – Set 3 (colourbar). The final number of included parameters per each control variable is annotated in the top marker.

Supplementary Figure 5. Quantified projection of population, educational attainment, and GDP using demographic and economic models. IIASA is the quantification from the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis³⁶. OECD is the quantification from the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development³⁷.

Supplementary Figure 6. Characterisation of the modelled pathways and their comparison against the projections of major demographic and economic models^{36,37} and integrated assessment models^{19,22,24,38,44-46}.

Continued.

Supplementary Figure 7. Progress towards ambitious (a, b, c) and weak (d, e, f) targets on indicators by 2030 (a, d), 2050 (b, e), and 2100 (c, f) across 50,000 simulated pathway realisations. The progress levels are defined according to Methods (main text). The stacked bar charts represent the progress across 50,000 realisations in all pathways combined. The percentage of the realisations at each progress level is marked inside the bars. We marked only the highest percentage of the progress. The arrows show the progress of the highest realisations per each pathway.

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